

ODD GRACEFULL LABELING FOR THE SUBDIVISION OF DOUBLE TRIANGLES GRAPHS

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to present some odd graceful graphs. In particular we show that an odd graceful labeling of the all subdivision of double triangular snakes ($2\Delta_k$ -snake). We also prove that the all subdivision of $2m\Delta_1$ -snake are odd graceful. Finally, we generalize the above two results (the all subdivision of $2m\Delta_k$ -snake are odd graceful).

KEYWORDS

Graph Labeling; Odd Graceful; Subdivision; Triangular Snakes

1.INTRODUCTION

The graphs considered here will be finite, undirected and simple. The symbols $V(G)$ and $E(G)$ will denote the vertex set and edge set of a graph G respectively. p and q denote the number of vertices and edges of G respectively.

A graph G of size q is odd-graceful, if there is an injection ϕ from $V(G)$ to $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2q-1\}$ such that, when each edge xy is assigned the label or weight $|\phi(x) - \phi(y)|$, the resulting edge labels are $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 2q-1\}$. This definition was introduced in 1991 by Gnanajothi [1] who proved that the class of odd graceful graphs lies between the class of graphs with ϕ -labelings and the class of bipartite graphs.

Rosa [2] defined a triangular snake(or Δ -snake) as a connected graph in which all blocks are triangles and the block-cut-point graph is a path. Let Δ_k -snake be a Δ -snake with k

blocks while $n\Delta_k$ -snake be a Δ -snake with k blocks and every block has n number of triangles with one common edge.

Illustration1:

Figure 1: Δ_3 -snake

$4\Delta_2$ -snake

Rosa[2] conjectured that Δ_k -snake (a snake with k blocks) is graceful for $n \equiv 0$ or $1 \pmod{4}$ and is nearly graceful otherwise. In 1989 Moulton [3] has proved Rosa's conjecture but using instead of nearly graceful labeling an stronger labeling named almost graceful.

A double triangular snake is a graph that formed by two triangular snakes have a common path. The harmonious labeling of double triangle snake introduced by Xi Yue et al [4]. It is known that the graphs which contain odd cycles are not odd graceful so Badr [5] used the subdivision notation for odd cycle in order to prove that the subdivision of linear triangular snakes are odd graceful. Badr et al [6] proved that the subdivision of ladders $S(L_n)$ is odd graceful.

In this paper we prove that an odd graceful labeling of the all subdivision of double triangular snakes ($2\Delta_k$ -snake). We also prove that the all subdivision of $2m\Delta_1$ -snake are odd graceful. Finally, we generalize the above two results (the all subdivision of $2m\Delta_k$ -snake are odd graceful).

2. MAIN RESULTS

Theorem 2.1 All the subdivision of double triangular snakes ($2\Delta_k$ -snake) are odd graceful.

Proof: Let $G = 2\Delta_k$ -snake has q edges and p vertices. The graph G consists of the vertices (u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{k+1}), (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k), (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_k) therefore we get the subdivision of double triangular snakes $S(G)$ by subdividing every edge of double triangular snakes $2\Delta_k$ -snake exactly once. Let y_i be the newly added vertex between u_i and u_{i+1} while w_{i1} and w_{i2} are newly added vertices between $w_i u_i$ and $w_i u_{i+1}$ respectively, where $1 \leq i \leq k$. Finally, v_{i1} and v_{i2} are newly added vertices between $v_i u_i$ and $v_i u_{i+1}$ respectively, such that $1 \leq i \leq k$. The graph $S(G)$ consists of the vertices (u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{k+1}), (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k), (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_k), ($w_{11}, w_{12}, w_{21}, w_{22}, \dots, w_{k1}, \dots, w_{k2}$), ($v_{11}, v_{12}, v_{21}, v_{22}, \dots, v_{k1}, v_{k2}$) and (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k) as shown in Figure 2. Clearly $S(G)$ has $q = 10k$ edges and $p = 8k + 1$ vertices.

Figure 2: the subdivision of double triangular snakes ($2\Delta_k$ -snake)

we prove that the subdivision of double triangular snakes $S(G)$ is odd graceful. Let us consider the following numbering ϕ of the vertices of the graph G :

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(u_i) &= 6(i-1) & 1 \leq i \leq k+1 \\ \phi(y_i) &= 2q-14i+11 & 1 \leq i \leq k \\ \phi(v_i) &= 6i-4 & 1 \leq i \leq k \\ \phi(v_{ij}) &= 2q-14i-8j+17 & 1 \leq i \leq k, j=1,2 \\ \phi(w_i) &= 6i+4 & 1 \leq i \leq k \\ \phi(w_{ij}) &= 2q-14i-6j+19 & 1 \leq i \leq k, j=1,2 \end{aligned}$$

$$(a) \quad \begin{aligned} \max_{v \in V} \phi(v) &= \max \left\{ \max_{1 \leq i \leq k+1} 6(i-1), \max_{1 \leq i \leq k} 2q-14i+11-1, \max_{1 \leq i \leq k} 6i-4, \max_{\substack{1 \leq j \leq 2 \\ 1 \leq i \leq k}} 2q-14i-8j+17, \right. \\ &\quad \left. \max_{1 \leq i \leq k} 6i+4, \max_{\substack{1 \leq j \leq 2 \\ 1 \leq i \leq k}} 2q-14i-6j+19 \right\} \end{aligned}$$

= $2q-1$, the maximum value of all odds .

Thus $\phi(v) \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2q-1\}$.

(b) Clearly ϕ is a one – to – one mapping from the vertex set of G to $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2q-1\}$.

(c) It remains to show that the labels of the edges of G are all the odd integers of the interval $[1, 2q-1]$.

The range of $\phi(u_i) - \phi(w_{i1}) = \{2q-20i+19; i=1,2,\dots,k\} = \{2q-1, 2q-21, \dots, 19\}$

The range of $\phi(u_i) - \phi(y_i) = \{2q-20i+17; i=1,2,\dots,k\} = \{2q-3, 2q-23, \dots, 17\}$

The range of $\phi(u_i) - \phi(v_{i1}) = \{2q-20i+15; i=1,2,3,\dots,k\} = \{2q-5, 2q-25, \dots, 15\}$

The range of $\phi(v_{i1}) - \phi(v_1) = \{2q-20i+13; i=1,2,3,\dots,k\} = \{2q-7, \dots, 13\}$

The range of $\phi(y_i) - \phi(u_{i+1}) = \{2q-20i+11; i=1,2,3,\dots,k\} = \{2q-9, \dots, 11\}$

The range of $\phi(w_{i1}) - \phi(w_i) = \{2q - 20i + 9 ; i = 1, 2, \dots, k\} = \{2q - 11, \dots, 9\}$
 The range of $\phi(w_{i2}) - \phi(u_{i+1}) = \{2q - 20i + 7 ; i = 1, 2, \dots, k\} = \{2q - 13, \dots, 7\}$
 The range of $\phi(v_i) - \phi(v_{i2}) = \{2q - 20i + 5 ; i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k\} = \{2q - 15, \dots, 5\}$
 The range of $\phi(w_{i2}) - \phi(w_i) = \{2q - 20i + 3 ; i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k\} = \{2q - 17, \dots, 3\}$
 The range of $\phi(v_{i2}) - \phi(u_{i+1}) = \{2q - 20i + 1 ; i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k\} = \{2q - 19, \dots, 1\}$
 Hence $\{\phi(u) - \phi(v) : uv \in E\} = \{1, 3, 5, \dots, 2q-1\}$ so that the subdivision of double triangular snakes ($2\Delta_k$ -snake) are odd graceful.

Illustration2:

Figure 3: odd-graceful labeling of the graph $S(2\Delta_4$ -snake).

Theorem 2.2 All the subdivision of $2m\Delta_1$ -snake are odd-graceful, where $m \geq 1$.

Proof :

Let $G = 2m\Delta_1$ -snake has q edges and p vertices. The graph G consists of the vertices $(u_1, u_2), (v_1^1, v_1^2, \dots, v_1^m), (w_1^1, w_1^2, \dots, w_1^m)$ therefore we get the subdivision of the graph $G, S(G)$, by subdividing every edge of the graph $G = 2m\Delta_k$ -snake exactly once. Let y_1 be the newly added vertex between u_1 and u_2 while w_{11}^i and w_{12}^i are newly added vertices between $w_1^i u_1$ and $w_1^i u_2$ respectively. Finally, v_{11}^i and v_{12}^i are newly added vertices between $v_1^i u_1$ and $v_1^i u_2$ respectively where $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$.

The graph $S(G)$ consists of the vertices $(u_1, u_2), (v_1^1, v_1^2, \dots, v_1^m), (w_1^1, w_1^2, \dots, w_1^m), y_1, (w_{11}^i, w_{12}^i, \dots, w_{12}^m)$ and $(v_{11}^i, v_{12}^i, \dots, v_{12}^m)$ as shown in Figure 4. Clearly $S(G)$ has $q = 8m + 2$ edges and $p = 6m + 3$ vertices.

Figure 4: the subdivision of $2m\Delta_1$ -snake

Let us consider the following numbering ϕ of the vertices of the graph G :

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(u_i) &= (4m+2)(i-1) & i &= 1,2 \\ \phi(y_1) &= 14m+3 \\ \phi(v_l^j) &= 4l-2 & 1 \leq l \leq m \\ \phi(w_l^j) &= 4(l+m)+2 & 1 \leq l \leq m \\ \phi(v_{lj}^j) &= 20m+2l+3-(8m+2)j & 2 \leq l \leq m, j=1,2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(v_{lj}^1) &= (18m+5)-(6m+2)j & j &= 1,2 \\ \phi(w_{lj}^j) &= (18m+2l+5)-(4m+2)j & j &= 1,2, 2 \leq l \leq m \end{aligned}$$

The edge labels will be as follows:

The vertices u_1 and w_{11}^l , $1 \leq l \leq m$, induce the edge labels $= \{14m+2l+3, 1 \leq l \leq m\}$
 $= \{14m+5, 14m+7, \dots, 16m+3\}$

The vertices u_1 and y_1 induce the edge labels $\{14m+3\}$

The vertices u_1 and v_{11}^l ; $1 \leq l \leq m$, induce the edge labels $\{12m+3, 12m+2l+1; 2 \leq l \leq m\}$
 $= \{12m+3, 12m+5, \dots, 14m+1\}$

The vertices v_{11}^l and v_{12}^l, y_1 and u_2, w_{11}^l and w_{12}^l induce the edge labels; $1 \leq l \leq m$:
 $\{12m+3-2l; 1 \leq l \leq m\}, \{10m+1\}, \{10m-2l+1; 1 \leq l \leq m\} = \{12m+1, 12m-1, \dots, 10m+1, 10m-1, \dots, 8m+1\}$.

The vertices w_{12}^l and u_2 induce the edge label $\{6m+2l-1; 1 \leq l \leq m\} = \{6m+1, 6m+3, \dots, 8m-1\}$

The vertices v_1^1 and v_{12}^1 induce the edge label $\{6m-1\}$.

The vertices w_{12}^l and w_{11}^l , induce the edge labels $\{6m-2l-1; 1 \leq l \leq m\} = \{6m-3, 6m-5, \dots, 4m-1\}$.

The vertices v_{12}^l and v_{11}^l ; $2 \leq l \leq m$ induce the edge labels $= \{4m-2l+1; 2 \leq l \leq m\}$
 $= \{4m-3, 4m-5, \dots, 2m+1\}$.

The vertices v_{12}^1 and u_2 induce the edge label $\{2m - 1\}$.

Finally the vertices v_{12}^l and u_2 induce the edge labels $\{2l-3 ; 2 \leq l \leq m\} = \{1,3,5,\dots,2m-3\}$.

Hence the graph $S(2m\Delta_1\text{-snake})$ is odd-graceful for each $m \geq 1$.

Theorem 2.3 All subdivision of $2m\Delta_k\text{-snake}$ are odd-graceful

Proof.

Let $G=2m\Delta_k\text{-snake}$ has q edges and p vertices. The graph G consists of the vertices $(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{k+1}), (v_1^1, v_1^2, \dots, v_1^m), (v_2^1, v_2^2, \dots, v_2^m), \dots, (v_k^1, v_k^2, \dots, v_k^m), (w_1^1, w_1^2, \dots, w_1^m), (w_2^1, w_2^2, \dots, w_2^m), \dots, (w_k^1, w_k^2, \dots, w_k^m)$ therefore we get the subdivision of double triangular snakes $S(G)$ by subdividing every edge of $2m\Delta_k\text{-snake}$ exactly once. Let y_l be the newly added vertex between u_1 and u_2 while w_{i1}^j and w_{i2}^j are newly added vertices between $w_i^j u_i$ and $w_i^j u_{i+1}$ respectively. Finally, v_{i1}^j and v_{i2}^j are newly added vertices between $v_i^j u_i$ and $v_i^j u_{i+1}$ respectively where $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$ and $j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$ (Figure 5). Clearly $S(G)$ has $q = k(8m + 2)$ edges.

Figure 5: the subdivision of $2m\Delta_k\text{-snake}$

Let us consider the following numbering ϕ of the vertices of the graph G :

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(u_i) &= (4m + 2)(i - 1) & 1 \leq i \leq k \\ \phi(w_i^l) &= (4m+2)i + 4l & 1 \leq i \leq k, 1 \leq l \leq m \\ \phi(v_i^l) &= (4m+2)i + 4(l-m-1) & 1 \leq i \leq k, 1 \leq l \leq m \\ \phi(y_i) &= 2q - (12m+2)i + 10m+1 ; & 1 \leq i \leq k, 1 \leq j \leq 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(w_{ij}^l) &= 2q-(12m+2)i - (4m+2)j + 14m + 2l + 3; 1 \leq i \leq k, 1 \leq j \leq 2, 1 \leq l \leq m \\ \phi(v_{ij}^l) &= 2q-(12m+2)i - (8m+2)j + 16m + 2l + 1; 1 \leq j \leq 2, 1 \leq l \leq m \\ \phi(v_{ij}^1) &= 2q-(12m+2)i - (6m+2)j + 14m + 3; 1 \leq i \leq k, 1 \leq j \leq 2 \end{aligned}$$

In a view of the above defined labeling pattern ϕ is odd-graceful for the graph $S(G)$. hence $S(G)$ is odd-graceful for all $m \geq 1, k \geq 1$.

Illustration 2,3 :

Figure 6: odd-graceful labeling of the graph $6\Delta_3$ -snake

3. CONCLUSION

Graceful and odd graceful of a graph are two entirely different concepts. A graph may possess one or both of these or neither. In the present work we show that an odd graceful labeling of the all subdivision of double triangular snakes ($2\Delta_k$ -snake). We also proved that the all subdivision of $2m\Delta_1$ -snake are odd graceful. Finally, we generalized the above two results (the all subdivision of $2m\Delta_k$ -snake are odd graceful).

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